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Improving short-term forecasting models for renewable energy
sources with key performance indicators

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Abstract

The use of renewable energy sources will be key to decrease pollution and reach the climate goals. Short-term forecasting is an important tool to counteract the downsides of using renewable energy sources, such as the unreliability of output. However, it is a complex problem and forecasting can be challenging. To determine the best evaluation metric to show which model is best suitable for a task key performance indicator can be used. In this research two approaches, Delphi and fuzzy AHP, are combined to research which key performance indicators are most important for developers and users. In addition, the results are shown with the use of process PLS. The findings are that interpretability is more important to users than previously anticipated and that the short-term forecasting field should include multi-criteria metrics to assess performance.

Keywords: short-term forecasting; key performance indicators; analytic hierarchy process; artificial intelligence; machine learning

Nomenclature

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial intelligence
AHP	Analytic hierarchy process
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
ANN	Artificial neural network
CR	Consistency ratio
CCS	Carbon capture sequestration
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GHG	Greenhouse gasses
KPI	Key performance indicator
LSTM	Long short term memory
ML	Machine learning
MAE	Mean absolute error
MSE	Mean squared error
NWP	Numerical weather prediction
RES	Renewable energy sources
RF	Random forest
SVM	Support vector machines

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1. Introduction

Environmental sustainability and sustainable development are becoming increasingly important for humankind (Emina, 2021; Jeronen, 2013). Global warming and environmental change result from environmental stress brought on by economic growth and rising energy demand (de Angelis et al., 2019; van Ruijven et al., 2019). Globally, nations and organizations have established objectives to counteract these changes through agreements such as the Paris Agreement. The primary cause of climate change is the release of greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) emissions by various industries (Hansen et al., 2000). The energy sector, which includes transportation, industry, electricity, and heat, accounts for 73.3% of all GHG emissions. With 15.83 billion tonne CO_{2-eq} in 2019, which is 31.82% of all global GHG emissions, electricity, and heat make up the majority of the energy sector's GHG emissions. Burning fossil fuels, which account for 84.3% of all energy generation, is the main cause of greenhouse gas emissions (Ritchie et al., 2020). It is vital to switch from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources in order to mitigate the effects of GHG emissions and meet the goals outlined in the Paris Agreement. For environmental sustainability and sustainable development, the switch to renewable energy sources (RES) is essential (Shaheen & Lipman, 2007).

To achieve the objectives outlined in agreements such as the Paris Agreement (UNFCCC, 2016) and the Kyoto Protocol (UNFCCC, 2012) to transition to renewable alternatives, the energy industry has a significant role to play. In 2010, RES generated 28.7% (IEA, 2022) of the world's electricity, with wind and solar energy contributing about 10% in 2021 (Bogdanov et al., 2021). The proportion of RES in the generation of electricity has been expanding steadily in recent years (Islam et al., 2014). Nevertheless, in 2021, this proportion only increased by 0.4 percentage points as a result of the rising electricity demand and consumption (IEA, 2022). Due to population increase and climate change, it is anticipated that the demand for electricity will rise in the upcoming years. This indicates that for progress to be made, the share of renewables must at least increase faster than the rise in electricity demand (Gielen et al., 2019).

RES are natural resources that can be replenished or naturally restored over time and do not deplete with their use. Using RES as opposed to conventional energy sources has a smaller negative impact on the environment and is more sustainable (Gielen et al., 2019; Islam et al., 2014). A combination of different options and techniques are required to utilize RES as effectively as possible, and these can vary from region to region depending on available indigenous resources and because new techniques are still being developed (Panwar et al., 2011). RES, such as wind, solar, biomass, hydropower, and geothermal are showing promise and can be used in many regions. Especially wind and solar energy have made great progress due to declining costs, while the costs of conventional fossil fuels have remained stable or have increased (Bogdanov et al., 2021; Wiser et al., 2021). The expectation that the energy sector will shift

toward renewables as a result of these changing costs is increasing. As a result, RES might emerge as a viable alternative and solution to reduce GHG emissions and increase sustainable development (Owusu & Asumadu-Sarkodie, 2016).

Given that RES must be connected to the energy network, it is typical for RES to be produced by energy providers or energy network operators (Gielen et al., 2019). In order to be used successfully RES such as solar panels on customers' homes and onshore or off-shore windmill parks must be placed, connected to the energy grid, and maintained by an organization. Energy providers have a range of choices to reduce GHG emissions over various time frames. The most appealing approaches are those that can be implemented quickly, such as increasing fossil fuel efficiency and lowering end-use energy and demand (Sorrell, 2015). Other strategies for providing more sustainable energy over a longer period of time include the use of nuclear energy and carbon capture sequestration (CCS) (Sorrell, 2015). In the long run, however, employing just short-term solutions will only partially fix the issue in terms of achieving the objectives set in pacts such as the Paris Agreement. The solution to the environmental challenges will probably be a combination of short-term implementations, a shift to renewable energy sources, and cutting-edge ideas like nuclear fusion (Fawzy et al., 2020).

The shift to RES is necessary due to legislation, rising energy demand, and fast technological advancements, which reduce the cost of renewables in comparison with conventional fossil fuels (Bogdanov et al., 2021). Nevertheless, this transition results in challenges for energy-providing companies (Sorrell, 2015). Energy network operators are forced to upgrade and modify their networks as a result of these rapidly changing situations. In addition, the new infrastructure has to be constructed, which involves high construction costs. The construction of RES facilities is necessary to meet the electricity demand. This results in new issues such as limited available space and ecosystem change or destruction (Owusu & Asumadu-Sarkodie, 2016). In addition, the energy production of RES, such as solar or wind, is unreliable because the production falters when the wind dies down or when it is cloudy (Tong et al., 2021). As a result, RES short-term forecasting is challenging and occasionally inaccurate (Mystakidis et al., 2023). In other circumstances, when demand is low, there may be an excess of renewable energy generation. In order to correct a shortfall or inconsistent output in the generation of renewable energy conventional energy generation backup methods must be used to balance the entire network (Ahmed et al., 2018). Most of the time, these reserves rely on fossil fuels. To be able to provide adequate electricity throughout the grid and to reduce their dependence on fossil fuels, energy providers must be able to estimate how much electricity will be generated by RES.

To predict RES electricity generation short-term forecasting can be used. Short-term forecasting for generating electricity using RES is still relatively new. There are two main approaches namely, conventional methods which are based on linear relationships, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques

such as machine learning (ML) (Teng et al., 2022a). The ML models include multiple techniques, such as long short-term memory (LSTM) and neural networks. These techniques have a high potential, but in practice do not always outperform the classical linear methods due to the novelty of the AI techniques (Abu-Salih et al., 2022; Mystakidis et al., 2023).

To evaluate the ML model's performance for short-term forecasting several metrics can be used. The metrics can be classified into three aspects, namely: accuracy-based, error-based, and informative-based metrics. Accuracy is about the predicted return compared to the effective return. Error-based metrics measure the error between the effective return and the predicted value of the model. Lastly, informative-based metrics are more additional information such as efficiency and CPU/GPU runtime (Dessain, 2022; Plevris et al., 2022).

To develop the best forecasting model that fits the user best looking only at the performance of the model as is currently the case is not enough. The user of the model can have various criteria for the forecasting model that cannot be measured with the standard metrics. Key performance indicators (KPIs) can be used to capture other various important measurable values.

1.1. Research Questions

The aim of this research is to find the key performance indicators (KPIs) between energy network operators and machine learning application providers to see if collaboration between these parties could improve the short-term forecasting models of renewable energy sources. Common machine learning models only focus on model accuracies or performance metrics to judge effectiveness, this work provides insight into the multi-criteria KPIs of machine learning in renewable energy application.

The main questions that are used for this research are as follows:

1. Which role can KPIs play in improving the evaluation process for short-term forecasting models?
2. How can machine learning application providers improve the short-term forecasting models of energy network operators employing KPIs?

Little research has been done into how to increase collaboration between energy network operators and ML application providers, which will be necessary to research climate goals and increase the use of RES. This research will show which criteria are important for short-term forecasting using AI models. With this knowledge the evaluation process can be expanded to include other criteria that are important for short-term forecasting, specifically if there is a mismatch between priorities of the energy network operator and ML application providers. This improved evaluation process would result in more specific aim of improvement for the models for both parties as it is clearer what the energy network providers want from the models.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1. AI models currently used for short-term forecasting for RES

The current literature shows that energy generation forecasting is a challenging problem since it involves weather parameters and historical data, and it is a non-linear problem (Akhtar et al., 2023). The emphasis on short-term forecasting is due to its usefulness in improved resource coordination. There are two main approaches for energy short-term forecasting: conventional models and AI models. The conventional models consist of linear and physical models and have been extensively used for RES forecasting. Examples of linear models include time series analysis models such as (S)ARIMA, ARMAX, and other autoregressive models (Abu-Salih et al., 2022). These models focus on time series and use historical data as input. An example of a physical model is the numerical weather prediction (NWP), which can be used to create models that can predict the atmosphere and weather conditions such as wind speed and direction and solar intensity.

For AI models, there are several ML models used, such as artificial neural networks (ANN), support vector machines (SVM), but also deep learning models, such as long-short term memory (LSTM). All these models offer different advantages for different situations. SVMs are effective for forecasting certain scenarios, especially when small datasets are used. LSTM models are useful for capturing temporal dependencies in time series data, which is especially important as most input data consists of time series data (Benti et al., 2023; Mystakidis et al., 2023).

There are many differences between conventional and AI models and each model has its strengths and weaknesses. Statistical models, such as ARIMA, are fairly easy to use, however, they do not support seasonal changes and complex nonlinear relations (Akhtar et al., 2023; Krechowicz et al., 2022). Some AI models such as LSTM support complex nonlinear relations but are far more difficult to train and need significantly more input data. AI models do not rely on explicit mathematical equations such as physical models, which enables them to capture the complex patterns in the input data for RES forecasting. In addition, AI models are more flexible and adaptable (Wei et al., 2019). Although AI models can be more sophisticated than conventional time-series models, conventional approaches are still in use since they occasionally outperform ML models (Abu-Salih et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2019).

AI models have considerable potential for short-term RES forecasting, but several challenges exist. The models need high-quality training data to ensure accurate predictions. In addition, the choice of which data to include can be difficult because there are several options and different arrangements in input data that can complicate the model, such as adding satellite data or not. Another issue is that AI models can be difficult for an operator to interpret due to their complexity and black-box architecture which means that the reasoning behind the predictions can be difficult to follow. Lastly, the computational time and

cost of the AI models can be high regarding training and usage (Krechowicz et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2019). Due to these challenges, it is necessary to consider data availability, model interpretability, and computational resources when choosing which model to use to ensure the most reliable and accurate short-term forecasting.

In this research, the general categories for each model will be used to generalize the outcome of this study. The first category of the model that will be looked at is the linear models, the second is pre-trained deep neural networks, the third is the convolutional neural network base models, the fourth is the long short-term memory base models, and the last is the ensemble models. These models are chosen based on a comparative study by Sharifzadeh et al. (2019) about current forecasting models.

2.2. Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

Key performance indicator (KPIs) are a quantifiable measure of performance over time for a specific objective (Kaganski et al. 2017). KPIs provide a way to assess performance, identify areas of improvement and make informed decisions. KPIs can be used in various domains for monitoring, controlling, and optimizing performances. There are multiple types of KPIs each with a different focus and purpose. The two main types are outcome-based and process-based KPIs. Outcome-based KPIs focus mainly on overall performance by assessing results and outcomes achieved by a company or organization, such as customer satisfaction or revenue. Process-based KPIs help clear up bottlenecks and improvement of processes by assessing the efficiency, effectiveness, and quality of processes (Efkarpidis et al., 2022; Meier et al., 2013).

By defining clear KPIs, a company or organization can determine which aspects or measurements are important for improving processes and results. If the current focus is not on the optimal factors and criteria, energy and money will be invested in the wrong aspect.

In the AI field, there has been little research done regarding KPIs. Current research focuses on how ML techniques can help predict and increase the quality of the KPIs (el Mazgualdi et al., 2021). ML techniques can help with the processing of large quantities of data, which can be useful for predicting KPIs as large quantities of text can be processed quickly. However, there is no research known to the researcher where KPIs are used to improve ML model.

2.3. Evaluation metrics

Model training for short-term forecasting of RES requires a large dataset that consists of multiple relevant variables such as historical energy production, historical weather data, satellite data, current weather conditions, and other contextual factors (Mystakidis et al., 2023). Accurate and representative

input data is key for training a reliable and accurate model. To create useful input data pre-processing steps can be used to enhance the quality of the data (Liao et al., 2022).

The standard approach to evaluate the performance of short-term forecasting models for RES is the use of statistical measures such as Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and coefficient of determination (R^2) (Tuohy et al., 2015). These metrics can all evaluate the performance of the model by determining the accuracy of the predictions of the model. In addition, various validation techniques such as time series validation and cross-validation can be used for assessing the robustness and generalizability of the model with unseen data (Liao et al., 2022).

With the training and validation process, AI models can be tested and compared. Accuracy and reliability are the most important factors in developing and implementing these models. The choice of correct features and evaluation metrics is essential for gaining the most knowledge for improving the forecasting accuracy of RES (Tuohy et al., 2015).

2.4. Conceptual model

In the field of short-term forecasting for RES, AI models have emerged as powerful tools for accurate predictions. However, evaluating the usefulness of these models requires appropriate metrics that go beyond traditional measures that focus solely on performance (Rawal et al., 2022). KPIs can have an effect in this field. KPIs can provide a framework for assessing the efficacy, efficiency, and impact of RES forecasting models while taking into consideration qualitative factors such as interpretability and accountability. KPIs are quantitative or qualitative metrics that fit with the forecasting process's strategic objectives and goals. By including KPIs in the evaluation process, AI models for short-term RES forecasts may be assessed in a broader and systematic manner.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), Support Vector Machines (SVMs), and Random Forests (RF) perform well in capturing the complex patterns and nonlinear correlations that come with RES forecasting. These models are often trained using historical energy production, historical weather data, satellite data, current weather conditions, and other contextual factors. However, assessing these models only on performance criteria such as mean absolute error (MAE) or root mean square error (RMSE) may not offer an accurate view of their actual performance. The reason is that these models can be complex and difficult to operate by companies and users whose expertise lies in other fields.

To create alternative evaluation metrics KPIs can be developed to measure the interpretability of AI models, ensuring that stakeholders and decision-makers can quicker understand the forecasts and underlying rationale. This increases transparency and confidence in the forecasting process, allowing for more effective interaction and decision-making. KPIs could, for example, assess the clarity and

comprehensibility of the model's outputs, the capacity to explain forecasts, or the transparency of the algorithms that make up the model.

If the AI models, KPIs, and evaluation metrics are combined a comprehensive evaluation framework can be made. This approach would use standard measures to analyze the quantitative performance of AI models while also including KPIs that highlight interpretability and accountability. This would mean that the evaluation metrics are not only focused on numerical accuracy, but also the other objectives of RES forecasting, such as interpretable and transparent models. The KPIs would help to create new quantitative and qualitative evaluation metrics to assess and later improve the AI models. These AI models would then provide feedback on which KPIs and metrics are important. This process can be seen in the conceptual model in Figure 1.

Lastly, the collaboration between the users, such as energy network operators and the developers would be easier if both parties know which KPIs are important for both sides. It would be easier to determine which elements the developers should focus on when developing the models.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of the linkage between AI models, evaluation metrics and KPIs.

3. Methods

The research used a quantitative method with multiple different data collection steps. The first step was to send a questionnaire to the customer side, the energy network operators. Then, a second questionnaire was sent to the energy network operators that used a multi-criteria decision-making method, called the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) (Saaty, 2004) to compare criteria for short-term forecasting models (Russo et al., 2015). After this, the supplier, the ML application provider, was asked via the same questionnaire about the different criteria for short-term forecasting models. Lastly, the supplier was asked how the models would score and give them weights for each criterion. After collecting the data, the data will be analyzed with the AHP method and the results will be shown with the method process PLS. An overview of the methods can be seen in Figure 2. The different parts are explained in the following paragraphs.

Figure 2. Illusion of methods used for data collection, analysis and outcome investigation.

3.1. Data collection method

3.1.1. Step 1: Delphi for criteria list

The first step of the research was to send a questionnaire that involved a list of important criteria for short-term forecasting models. The questionnaire had a pre-made list of criteria based on literature (de Hond, 2022; Rawal et al., 2022) and the Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) for self-assessment (European Commission, 2020). Initially, the list contained 27 criteria, however, due to the lack of structure and the required data for the AHP method in step 2, this list could not be used in the current form. For the AHP, all criteria would have to be compared with each other. For 27 criteria, this would mean 378 comparisons. However, if a hierarchy is established where the criteria are divided into main criteria with sub criteria, only the sub criteria would have to be compared with each other, and the number of comparisons would significantly decrease. The initial list was divided into four main criteria, *security*, *performance*, *interpretability*, *accountability*, and 23 sub criteria. The main criteria were chosen based on general import factors for models in the AI field (Rawal et al., 2022). The other criteria were then subdivided into the four main criteria. The initial list of criteria can be found in Table 1. Additional explanation of the meaning of each sub criteria can be found in Appendix A.

Table 1. Initial list of criteria

Criteria	Sub criteria
Security	Secure against model inversion attack
	User of the model cannot access private data (model privacy)
Interpretability	Be able to link the model input to output in a visual way
	Output is in a logical range
	Able to assess the quality of input data
	Be able to show feature importance and selection of input data
	Detecting and revealing anomalies in input data
	Graphical interface completeness
	Easy to (re)implement
	Able to trace past decision-making
	Risk minimalization by human overseeing (Human in the loop)
	Easy to incorporate with standard open source material
Performance	Able to finetune during operation
	Model accuracy
	Amount of input data necessary
	Versatile and adaptable model
	Computational efficiency/time
	Robustness
	Large forecasting horizon
Accountability	FAIR use of data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable)
	Focus on environmental gain
	Unparameterized model

To make the final list of criteria, the participants were sent a questionnaire with the criteria and had to indicate which criteria were useful and which should be removed from the list. This approach was loosely based on the Delphi method (Dalkey, 1963; Grisham, 2009). The Delphi method entails three rounds of consensus building about the criteria with the use of a Likert scale from one to five. Participants rate the criteria and after each round, the criteria with a score of two or lower are deleted from the list. In the first round, the participants have the option to add criteria to the list if they deemed them important. This option is not available in the second and third rounds as this could lengthen the process indefinitely. If there is a consensus, or in other words, all criteria are scored above two, before the third round, the process will be finalized beforehand. However, due to time constraints, the Delphi method with multiple rounds could not take place. Instead, only one round of Delphi was performed. The participants were sent the initial list of criteria and had to indicate which criteria they wanted to add and which criteria should be removed. The Likert scale was not used. After the first round, there was consensus between the experts, and the criteria were then respectively added and removed to create the final list of criteria. An example of a criterion that was removed was *large forecasting horizon* from the main criteria *performance* and an example of a criterion that was added was *explainability of forecasted values and process* from the main criteria *interpretability*. The resulting list can be found in Appendix B.

3.1.2. Step 2: Compare criteria

The second step in this research is to compare the criteria of step 1. This is done via a second questionnaire which was sent to the energy network operator participants who used the AHP method to compare the various criteria systematically. The AHP method can be seen in Figure 2 by the parts within the dashed block. The first step in the AHP method was to define the goal, criteria, and alternatives. The goal is similar to the research objective: to find the most important criteria for models for short-term forecasting for RES and subsequently find which criteria have the largest impact to determine model performance. The criteria used were the criteria from the resulting list from the questionnaire in the previous step. The alternatives are the various options that are available to reach the goal. In this case, the alternatives were the various short-term forecasting models that could be used. The models that were considered were given weights for each criterion with the use of a questionnaire in step three. The AHP model can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Analytical Hierarchical Process (AHP) model demonstrating overall goal, main criteria, sub criteria and model categories.

The next step in the AHP method was to conduct the questionnaire with the participants from the energy network operators to compare the criteria. The questionnaire first asked the participants to compare the four main criteria *security*, *performance*, *interpretability* and *accountability* with each other on a scale from one to nine, because of the rules of AHP a Likert scale from one to nine is used. Next, the sub criteria per main criteria were compared with each other, again using a Likert scale from one to nine.

3.1.3. Step 3: Models

The third step in this research was to send a questionnaire to the ML application provider about which kind of AI models or categories to include in the AHP method. This step had to be done by the ML application provider as they are the experts with respect to the models. The questionnaire covered the various short-term forecasting models that can be used as alternatives. The initial list consisted of different categories of short-term forecasting models (Rawal et al., 2022). The participant was asked which categories of models should be considered for forecasting RES. The resulting list of five categories of models which consisted of *linear models*, *pretrained deep neural network models*, *ensembled models*, *convolutional neural network based models*, and *long short-term memory base models*, was then used in step 4.

3.1.4. Step 4: Model weights

The last step for data collection was to send a questionnaire to the ML application provider as well. The goal of this questionnaire was to give weights to the models that were selected in the questionnaire of

step 3. Every model category had to have a score for each pairwise comparison with the other model categories for each criterion. The aim was to have the participant compare each model category with the other model categories for each criterion. However, due to the large number of criteria, this would mean roughly 230 comparisons. Instead, the data was gathered by interviewing the participant and scoring the model categories on a scale from one to nine for each criterion. These scores were then changed into fractions for the AHP method as weights for the models. The fractions were made by dividing the score of the model category by the score of the second model category.

3.2. Data analysis

The data of the questionnaires are first exported from Qualtrics to Jupyter Notebook. To program the analysis, Python is used. To implement the AHP method, first, the pairwise comparisons are transformed into matrices for each level of the hierarchy. This means that a matrix is made for the four main criteria together and for each main criterion separately. The matrices for the four main criteria from the participants can be seen in Appendix C.

Next, the pairwise comparisons between the forecasting models for each criterion are transformed into matrices. Lastly, the hierarchy is made where the hierarchy represents the decision problem. In the hierarchy, the sub criteria are the children of the main criteria. Finally, the weights for the models, the criteria, and the consistency ratio can be extracted.

The AHP method uses a consistency ratio (CR) to determine if the output is consistent. If the score is too high ($CR > 0.1$), this would mean that there was an inconsistency in the judgments during the pairwise comparisons. The weights for the elements in the hierarchy are not well aligned with each other, which causes conflicting priorities. The CR is calculated by comparing the ratio of its consistency index to the corresponding random index value (Saaty, 2004).

A solution to a high CR can be an extension of AHP called, fuzzy AHP (Zadeh et al., 1996) which is similar to AHP but they differ in the precision of the input data and the weights. Fuzzy AHP incorporates fuzzy logic to deal with uncertain and imprecise judgments and mitigate the ambiguity of individual thinking. When there is a low number of experts, there can be a high variability, which a fuzzy method can counteract by using distributions. An overview of the fuzzy AHP method can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Block diagram of fuzzy AHP phase process (adapted from Dwi Putra et al., 2018)

In a fuzzy method, instead of one number for each pairwise comparison for the criteria, there are three numbers, namely a minimum, average, and maximum value. These values are coming from the pairwise comparisons of the participants (step 2). The lowest score of the participants was the minimum value, the average of the scores was the average value and the highest score was the maximum value. With these three values, a triangular function is created where the AHP process can be looped with a value from within that triangle. An example can be seen in Figure 5. This approach is called a Monte Carlo simulation that “uses random sampling from a probability density function to mimic the operations of complex systems.” (Harrison et al., 2010). In the Monte Carlo simulation the sampling from the triangle function is performed one thousand times as input for the fuzzy AHP method.

Figure 5. The triangle membership function of the fuzzy AHP method (adapted from Kazemi et al., 2015)

Lastly, a method called process PLS (van Kollenburg et al., 2021; Teng, 2022b) is used to estimate and show the relationship between the main criteria and the different models. Process PLS can be used to “analyze multi-block, multistep and/or multidimensional processes and to prioritize effects based on

predictive power.” (van Kollenburg et al., 2021). The method starts with specifying the model, then the latent variable estimation, and lastly the coefficient calculation. The method is able to optimize the covariance between latent variables with a low computational complexity and show the relationship between blocks with explained variance.

3.3. Participants

The participants of the first two steps that compared the criteria for the short-term forecasting models are an employee of the energy network operator, a researcher in the field of short-term forecasting, and an employee of the ML application provider. The participant for the third and fourth steps was an employee of the ML application provider, who determined which categories of models to use and gave weights for the different models regarding all the criteria.

3.4. Interview setup

For the data collection steps, all the questionnaires were held online with the researcher present to explain the criteria where necessary. All the questionnaires were made in Qualtrics. The initial questionnaire for step 1 to determine the list of criteria took around three to five minutes to fill in. The questionnaire for step 2 to compare all the criteria was made up of matrix tables to pairwise compare all criteria and took the participants between thirty and sixty minutes.

Filling in the questionnaire for step 3 to determine the list of model categories took four minutes and the questionnaire for step 4 for the weights of each model category for each criterion took the participant 27 minutes.

4. Results

4.1. Criteria

From the fuzzy AHP method, histograms are created. In these histograms, the distribution for the criteria can be seen. The distributions can capture more of the uncertainty of the input data. As can be seen in Figure 6, the value of the four main criteria peaks for *security* at 0.14, for *interpretability* at 0.35, for *performance* at 0.19, and *accountability* at 0.28. Important to note is that the criteria have a, roughly even, large spread of 0.25, except *security* which has a smaller spread of 0.15. This is in line with current research that suggests that *interpretability* is essential to explain the black-box models (Linardatos et al., 2020). To create accountable AI models, it is important that the models can be interpreted, explained and accounted for (Rawal et al., 2022). However, there is a trade-off between *performance* and *interpretability* and *accountability* (Linardatos et al., 2020). This finding of current literature can be seen in Figure 9, as the linear and ensembled models score highest, which are simpler and can be interpreted more easily, while the state-of-the-art model categories score lower overall, even though they have a higher *performance* (Rawal et al., 2022).

Figure 6. Histogram of the four main criteria

In Figure 7 can be seen that the criterion that has the highest score in the main criterion of *security* is *secure against model inversion attack*. The participants indicated that there is a negligible security risk for users accessing private data as the models use public data or the users are part of the company, but there is a fear that other companies reproduce the models via inversion methods. In Figure 8 can be seen that the criterion that has the highest score for *interpretability* is *output is in a logical range*.

Examining the model's ability to generate logical results is a crucial step in understanding how to interpret it. The model is not operating correctly or misinterpreting the data if the result is not within a logical range. In Figure 9 can be seen that for *performance*, the criterion with the highest score is *able to finetune during operation*, while *accuracy* and *robustness* both score slightly lower. *Accuracy* and *robustness* are traditionally important criteria to determine a model's performance. The participants show that human control over the process by tweaking the model during operation is important. For *accountability*, the criterion with the highest score is *FAIR use of data*.

Figure 7. Histogram of security sub criteria

Figure 8. Histogram of interpretability sub criteria

Figure 9. Histogram of performance sub criteria

Figure 10. Histogram of accountability sub criteria

4.2. Models

In terms of the model categories, as can be seen in Figure 11, there is a notable overlap between *linear models* and *ensembled models*, both of which have the main peak at about 0.20 and a wider spread than the others model categories, namely 0.15 instead of 0.1. Additionally, the other model categories scarcely overlap. According to current literature (Linardatos et al., 2020) users of AI models can prefer simpler but more interpretable models over complex high performing models. Particularly in fields where fairness or transparency are essential (Hardt et al., 2016), it can be crucial to be able identify the source of the output to improve the (future) forecasts and the models.

Figure 11. Histogram of model categories

Figure 12 depicts the process PLS plots for the model categories. The latent variable estimations are the nodes, which include the four main criteria and a model category and the edges represent the path coefficients explained variance between the blocks. It is important to note that the plots in Figure 12 give the explained variance importance given that the model is selected. This is relevant as the model selection alters the importance of the criteria. Figure 6 shows that the criterion *security* has the lowest score before the model is chosen in the AHP method. In comparison, after choosing a model, *security*, as can be observed in all process PLS models, is more important since it influences all other nodes, including the models. This demonstrates that when the model is selected, the interdependence of criteria is different than the initial criteria score from Figure 6 indicates.

In Figure 12 (a) can be that *interpretability* has the highest effect on the short-term forecasting model categories, namely 0.46 for *linear models*, in Figure 12 (b) 0.45 for *ensemble models*, in Figure 12 (d) 0.56 for *convolutional neural network base model* and in Figure 12 (e) 0.52 for *long short-term memory base model*, except for Figure 12 (c) *pre-trained deep neural networks* where *security* has the highest effect of 0.57 followed by *performance* with 0.26. Important to note is that *interpretability* has a large effect on *performance* and *accountability* for all model categories. This is important as “the total effect of one block on another consists of the direct effect plus any indirect effects” (Alwin & Hauser, 1975).

Figure 12. Process PLS plots for the four main criteria with a model category: (a) linear models, (b) ensembled models, (c) pretrained deep neural networks, (d) Convolutional neural network base models, (e) Long short-term memory base models

5. Discussion

5.1. Interpretation of Analysis

To increase the collaboration between the energy network operators and ML application providers the focus should be on the development of interpretable models (Akhtar et al., 2023). This can be deduced from the results where *interpretability* is the most important criterion of the four main criteria, followed by *accountability*, then *performance*, and lastly *security*. However, it is not clear how certain this conclusion is, due to the large spread and overlapping of the distributions. From the results can be deduced that the participants value *interpretability* and less complex models over *performance* and accuracy. However, due to the complex nature of short-term forecasting and the input data the focus for the ML application providers should be to develop hybrid models that incorporate different techniques to combine the *interpretability* of linear models and the *performance* of state-of-the-art models.

Due to the overlap between linear models and ensembled models, additional research is needed to identify which model is optimal for energy network operators and ML application providers by focusing on the differences between these two model categories. Due to their simplicity and ease of use, linear models are the best fit for energy network operators. In comparison, in order to get the best forecasts, ensemble models mix multiple models and techniques, which could give a slight edge over linear models. Energy network operators could improve their models by incorporating methods from the ensembled models (Akhtar et al., 2023).

KPIs such as the sub criteria used in this research can play a major role in improving the evaluation process for short-term forecasting to shift from focusing solely on performance-based metrics to other metrics, such as *accountability* and *interpretability* based metrics (Linardatos et al., 2020). This counteracts the focus of current literature on quantitative evaluation metrics (González-Sopeña et al., 2021; Tuohy et al., 2015). *Performance* should not decrease in favour of *interpretability* or *accountability* because then the added value of collaboration between energy network operators and ML application providers could decrease, but the focus should shift towards including different evaluation metrics than solely MAE or RMSE. However, more research is necessary to determine the extent of the importance of *interpretability* for the short-term forecasting field, but also other fields where AI models are used.

5.2. Limitations

Most of the limitations of this study are the result of the relatively new field of this research. Because it is a new and active field of research, numerous papers were published during this research that could have provided better information during the making of this research. To give an example, the paper of

Akhtar et al. (2023), which explained each model category in detail, could have provided different criteria for the initial criteria list or different model categories. This could have helped provide a more fitting initial list of criteria or model categories which would have saved time.

Furthermore, the novelty of this field results in a limited number of experts. As there are few experts in the field of short-term energy forecasting for developing and using these models, especially working for the energy network operator used in this research, there was only a small number of participants that could be interviewed. A similar problem was encountered with the supplier, the ML application provider. It is, therefore, important to note that the results cannot be generalized to other fields or even to other energy network operators working with ML application providers. Nevertheless, the results are still valid to answer the research question, as the fuzzy AHP provides a distributed view of the output by looping one thousand times through the AHP to counter the uncertainty of the input data.

Another limitation is regarding the combination of the Delphi method and (fuzzy) AHP. Because of the time constraints, there was not enough time to complete all steps of both methods in the way prescribed in the original methods. This resulted in some of the steps of the Delphi method and AHP needing to be left out or altered. The main problem resulting from this limitation is regarding the list of criteria. Because of time constraints, there was only one round of the Delphi method. This resulted in some problems. The first problem was that, because of some miscommunication, a participant made recommendations for changes after the deadline. Therefore, their recommended changes, such as adding the criteria scalability, could not be implemented. In addition, during the questionnaires of step 2, it became clear that some of the criteria were not applicable due to their focus on the preprocessing steps instead of the model. In hindsight, more explanation was needed regarding the criteria and what they would be used for during the later stages of this research so that participants could have better determined whether a criterion was useful. These problems caused the initial list of criteria to include criteria that were less useful to determine KPIs and the ranking of the models.

The last limitation of this research is regarding the focus of the two companies at which questionnaires were conducted. The energy network operator's focus is on both solar and wind energy, while the ML application provider only concentrates on solar energy. This could potentially have an effect on the data, as the questionnaire filled in by the ML application provider has a bias for solar energy. As a result, the data of the weights of the models, specifically how well a model scores on a particular criterion, is made with regard to solar energy, not particularly for wind energy. As this research has an exploratory focus, trying to find out whether a collaboration between energy network operators and machine learning application providers could be valuable, this difference between the focus of the two companies is not a big problem. Collaboration between these companies still has advantages

As could be seen in the results, a collaboration between these companies could have advantages. When companies want collaboration, they should keep in mind that their focus is aligned in order to optimize the outcome of the collaboration. The results could give an indication of what the ML application providers should focus on to align their focus with the energy network operators.

5.3. Future research

This research has made a start with the combination of hybrid Delphi with AHP interviews on short-term forecasting. The results showed that this method could be useful in cases where there are few experts and where an array of different techniques and models can be used and developed. As this is a new approach and there were time constraints, more research should be conducted regarding the combination of these two methods in order to create an efficient method to find the optimal criteria to measure the usefulness of the models.

Furthermore, the criteria used in this research could be different for different energy network operators and machine-learning model providers. For other fields where AI models are used, the important criteria could be vastly different. This is why the Delphi process is vital to come up with the initial list of criteria that will be used throughout the research. Therefore, in future research, the steps in the Delphi method should be completed with a consensus before starting with the (fuzzy) AHP method.

6. Conclusion

This study sought to identify the KPIs between energy network operators and ML application providers in order to enhance cooperation between these parties and, as a result, improve short-term forecasting of RES and RES use. The collaboration can be vital to increase the use of RES and reach climate goals.

The findings support recent literature by demonstrating that *interpretability*—rather than just *performance*—is important to energy network providers. With these findings this research shows that collaboration between energy network operators and ML application providers could strengthen by focusing on KPIs that are important for both parties. The KPIs show that multi-criteria from *accountability* and *interpretability* to assess performance instead of only performance based metrics are important for determine the overall performance of a short-term forecasting model.

7. References

- Abu-Salih, B., Wongthongtham, P., Morrison, G., Coutinho, K., Al-Okaily, M., & Huneiti, A. (2022). Short-term renewable energy consumption and generation forecasting: A case study of Western Australia. *Heliyon*, 8(3), e09152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09152>
- Ahmed, S. U., Ahmed, S. U., & Memon, A. (2018). Renewable Energy's Reliability Issue and Possible Solutions: A Meta-Analytic Review. *University of Sindh Journal of Information and Communication Technology*.
- Akhtar, S., Shahzad, S., Zaheer, A., Ullah, H. S., Kilic, H., Gono, R., Jasiński, M., & Leonowicz, Z. (2023). Short-Term Load Forecasting Models: A Review of Challenges, Progress, and the Road Ahead. *Energies*, 16(10), 4060. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16104060>
- Alwin, D. F., & Hauser, R. M. (1975). The Decomposition of Effects in Path Analysis. *American Sociological Review*, 40(1), 37. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2094445>
- Benti, N. E., Chaka, M. D., & Semie, A. G. (2023). Forecasting Renewable Energy Generation with Machine Learning and Deep Learning: Current Advances and Future Prospects. *Sustainability*, 15(9), 7087. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097087>
- Bogdanov, D., Ram, M., Aghahosseini, A., Gulagi, A., Oyewo, A. S., Child, M., Caldera, U., Sadovskaia, K., Farfan, J., de Souza Noel Simas Barbosa, L., Fasihi, M., Khalili, S., Traber, T., & Breyer, C. (2021). Low-cost renewable electricity as the key driver of the global energy transition towards sustainability. *Energy*, 227, 120467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.120467>
- de Angelis, E. M., di Giacomo, M., & Vannoni, D. (2019). Climate Change and Economic Growth: The Role of Environmental Policy Stringency. *Sustainability*, 11(8), 2273. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11082273>
- de Hond, A. A. H., Leeuwenberg, A. M., Hooft, L., Kant, I. M. J., Nijman, S. W. J., van Os, H. J. A., Aardoom, J. J., Debray, T. P. A., Schuit, E., van Smeden, M., Reitsma, J. B., Steyerberg, E. W., Chavannes, N. H., & Moons, K. G. M. (2022). Guidelines and quality criteria for artificial intelligence-based prediction models in healthcare: a scoping review. *Npj Digital Medicine*, 5(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-021-00549-7>
- Dalkey, N., & Helmer, O. (1963). An experimental application of the Delphi method to the use of experts. *Management Science*, 9, 458–467.
- Dessain, J. (2022). Machine learning models predicting returns: Why most popular performance metrics are misleading and proposal for an efficient metric. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 199, 116970. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.116970>
- Dwi Putra, M. S., Andryana, S., Fauziah, & Gunaryati, A. (2018). Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process Method to Determine the Quality of Gemstones. *Advances in Fuzzy Systems*, 2018, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/9094380>
- Efkarpidis, N., Goranović, A., Yang, C.-W., Geidl, M., Herbst, I., Wilker, S., & Sauter, T. (2022). A Generic Framework for the Definition of Key Performance Indicators for Smart Energy Systems at Different Scales. *Energies*, 15(4), 1289. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15041289>
- el Mazgualdi, C., Masrou, T., el Hassani, I., & Khoudi, A. (2021). Machine learning for KPIs prediction: a case study of the overall equipment effectiveness within the automotive industry. *Soft Computing*, 25(4), 2891–2909. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-020-05348-y>

- Emina, K. A. (2021). SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND THE FUTURE GENERATIONS. *Social Sciences, Humanities and Education Journal (SHE Journal)*, 2(1), 57. <https://doi.org/10.25273/she.v2i1.8611>
- European Commission. (2020). *Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) for self-assessment*. High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
- Fawzy, S., Osman, A. I., Doran, J., & Rooney, D. W. (2020). Strategies for mitigation of climate change: a review. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 18(6), 2069–2094. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-020-01059-w>
- Gielen, D., Boshell, F., Saygin, D., Bazilian, M. D., Wagner, N., & Gorini, R. (2019). The role of renewable energy in the global energy transformation. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 24, 38–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2019.01.006>
- González-Sopeña, J. M., Pakrashi, V., & Ghosh, B. (2021). An overview of performance evaluation metrics for short-term statistical wind power forecasting. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 138, 110515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110515>
- Grisham, T. (2009). The Delphi technique: a method for testing complex and multifaceted topics. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 2(1), 112–130. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17538370910930545>
- Hansen, J., Sato, M., Ruedy, R., Lacis, A., & Oinas, V. (2000). Global warming in the twenty-first century: An alternative scenario. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 97(18), 9875–9880. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.170278997>
- Hardt, M., Price, E., & Srebro, N. (2016). Equality of opportunity in supervised learning. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 29.
- Harrison, R. L., Granja, C., & Leroy, C. (2010). *Introduction to Monte Carlo Simulation*. 17–21. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3295638>
- IEA. (2022). *Renewable electricity*. <https://www.iea.org/reports/renewable-electricity>.
- Islam, M. A., Hasanuzzaman, M., Rahim, N. A., Nahar, A., & Hosenuzzaman, M. (2014). Global Renewable Energy-Based Electricity Generation and Smart Grid System for Energy Security. *The Scientific World Journal*, 2014, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/197136>
- Jeronen, E. (2013). Sustainability and Sustainable Development. In *Encyclopedia of Corporate Social Responsibility* (pp. 2370–2378). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-28036-8_662
- Kaganski, S., Majak, J., Karjust, K., & Toompalu, S. (2017). Implementation of Key Performance Indicators Selection Model as Part of the Enterprise Analysis Model. *Procedia CIRP*, 63, 283–288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2017.03.143>
- Kazemi, S., Homayouni, S. M., & Jahangiri, J. (2015). A Fuzzy Delphi-Analytical Hierarchy Process Approach for Ranking of Effective Material Selection Criteria. *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, 2015, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/845346>
- Krechowicz, A., Krechowicz, M., & Poczeta, K. (2022). Machine Learning Approaches to Predict Electricity Production from Renewable Energy Sources. *Energies*, 15(23), 9146. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15239146>

- Liao, W., Bak-Jensen, B., Pillai, J. R., Yang, Z., & Liu, K. (2022). Short-term power prediction for renewable energy using hybrid graph convolutional network and long short-term memory approach. *Electric Power Systems Research*, 211, 108614. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2022.108614>
- Linardatos, P., Papastefanopoulos, V., & Kotsiantis, S. (2020). Explainable AI: A Review of Machine Learning Interpretability Methods. *Entropy*, 23(1), 18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e23010018>
- Meier, H., Lagemann, H., Morlock, F., & Rathmann, C. (2013). Key Performance Indicators for Assessing the Planning and Delivery of Industrial Services. *Procedia CIRP*, 11, 99–104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2013.07.056>
- Mystakidis, A., Ntozi, E., Afentoulis, K., Koukaras, P., Gkaidatzis, P., Ioannidis, D., Tjortjis, C., & Tzovaras, D. (2023). Energy generation forecasting: elevating performance with machine and deep learning. *Computing*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00607-023-01164-y>
- Owusu, P. A., & Asumadu-Sarkodie, S. (2016). A review of renewable energy sources, sustainability issues and climate change mitigation. *Cogent Engineering*, 3(1), 1167990. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311916.2016.1167990>
- Panwar, N. L., Kaushik, S. C., & Kothari, S. (2011). Role of renewable energy sources in environmental protection: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 15(3), 1513–1524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2010.11.037>
- Parmenter, D. (2019). *Key Performance Indicators: Developing, Implementing, and Using Winning KPIs* (4th edition). John Wiley and sons Inc.
- Plevris, V., Solorzano, G., Bakas, N., & ben Seghier, M. (2022). Investigation of performance metrics in regression analysis and machine learning-based prediction models. *8th European Congress on Computational Methods in Applied Sciences and Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.23967/eccomas.2022.155>
- Rawal, A., McCoy, J., Rawat, D. B., Sadler, B. M., & Amant, R. st. (2022). Recent Advances in Trustworthy Explainable Artificial Intelligence: Status, Challenges, and Perspectives. *IEEE Transactions on Artificial Intelligence*, 3(6), 852–866. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAI.2021.3133846>
- Ritchie, H., Roser, M., & Rosado, R. (2020). *CO₂ and Greenhouse Gas Emissions*. Our World in Data.
- Russo, R. de F. S. M., & Camanho, R. (2015). Criteria in AHP: A Systematic Review of Literature. *Procedia Computer Science*, 55, 1123–1132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2015.07.081>
- Saaty, T. L. (2004). Decision making — the Analytic Hierarchy and Network Processes (AHP/ANP). *Journal of Systems Science and Systems Engineering*, 13(1), 1–35. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11518-006-0151-5>
- Saaty, T. L. (2006). The Analytic Network Process. In *Decision Making with the Analytic Network Process* (Vol. 95, pp. 1–26). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/0-387-33987-6_1
- Shaheen, S. A., & Lipman, T. E. (2007). REDUCING GREENHOUSE EMISSIONS AND FUEL CONSUMPTION. *IATSS Research*, 31(1), 6–20. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0386-1112\(14\)60179-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0386-1112(14)60179-5)
- Sharifzadeh, M., Sikinioti-Lock, A., & Shah, N. (2019). Machine-learning methods for integrated renewable power generation: A comparative study of artificial neural networks, support vector

- regression, and Gaussian Process Regression. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 108, 513–538. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.03.040>
- Sorrell, S. (2015). Reducing energy demand: A review of issues, challenges and approaches. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 47, 74–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.03.002>
- Teng, S. Y., van Nooten, C. C., van Doorn, J. M., Ottenbros, A., Huijbregts, M., & Jansen, J. J. (2022a). Improving Near Real-Time Predictions of Renewable Electricity Production at Substation Level (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7991654>
- Teng, S. Y. (2022b). tsyet12/ProcessPLS:An Implementation of ProcessPLS in Python, Zenodo Release (zenodo). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7074754>
- Tong, D., Farnham, D. J., Duan, L., Zhang, Q., Lewis, N. S., Caldeira, K., & Davis, S. J. (2021). Geophysical constraints on the reliability of solar and wind power worldwide. *Nature Communications*, 12(1), 6146. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-26355-z>
- Tuohy, A., Zack, J., Haupt, S. E., Sharp, J., Ahlstrom, M., Dise, S., Gritmit, E., Mohrlen, C., Lange, M., Casado, M. G., Black, J., Marquis, M., & Collier, C. (2015). Solar Forecasting: Methods, Challenges, and Performance. *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, 13(6), 50–59. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MPE.2015.2461351>
- UNFCCC. (2016). *The Paris Agreement*. https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement?Gclid=CjwKCAiAr4GgBhBFEiwAgwORrUpEO29NDW-WRxsBBxbvijaVvhFHwEqRBrhQvrt1jEHb1oBS1RtqnRoCqygQAvD_BwE.
- UNFCCC. (2012). *What is the Kyoto Protocol?* https://unfccc.int/Kyoto_protocol.
- van Kollenburg, G., Bouman, R., Offermans, T., Gerretzen, J., Buydens, L., van Manen, H.-J., & Jansen, J. (2021). Process PLS: Incorporating substantive knowledge into the predictive modelling of multiblock, multistep, multidimensional and multicollinear process data. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 154, 107466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2021.107466>
- van Ruijven, B. J., de Cian, E., & Sue Wing, I. (2019). Amplification of future energy demand growth due to climate change. *Nature Communications*, 10(1), 2762. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-10399-3>
- Wei, N., Li, C., Peng, X., Zeng, F., & Lu, X. (2019). Conventional models and artificial intelligence-based models for energy consumption forecasting: A review. *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering*, 181, 106187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petrol.2019.106187>
- Wiser, R., Rand, J., Seel, J., Beiter, P., Baker, E., Lantz, E., & Gilman, P. (2021). Expert elicitation survey predicts 37% to 49% declines in wind energy costs by 2050. *Nature Energy*, 6(5), 555–565. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-021-00810-z>
- Zadeh, L. A., Klir, G. J., & Yuan, B. (1996). *Fuzzy sets, fuzzy logic, and fuzzy systems: selected papers* (Vol. 6). World scientific.

8. Appendix

Appendix A

Initial criteria list

1. Security
 - a. Secure against model inversion attack (model complexity high enough that the model cannot be reproduced from the output, linear model is easy to replicate using output)
 - b. User of the model cannot access private data (model privacy) (Input data is not shared through the model/ cannot be accessed through the model)
2. Interpretability
 - a. Be able to link the model input to output in a visual way (no black box, able to follow reasons/logic of the model)
 - b. Output is in a logical range (the output of the model is consistent even with varying input)
 - c. Able to assess the quality of input data (model can determine the quality of the input data and give a proper indication)
 - d. Be able to show feature importance and selection of input data (the reasoning of the model can be followed on how it interprets and uses the input data)
 - e. Detecting and revealing anomalies in input data (model can determine the level of bias in the input data)
 - f. Graphical interface completeness (the model interface is easy to use)
 - g. Easy to (re)implement (model is easy to use with few complex operations)
 - h. Able to trace past decision-making (the output can be traced back to the specific input data)
 - i. Risk minimalization by human overseeing (Human in the loop) (Errors are stated and can be fixed by a human operator)
 - j. Easy to incorporate with standard open source material (model can be used in combination with other (already existing) models)
3. Performance
 - a. Able to finetune during operation (able to control the model during the whole process)
 - b. Model accuracy (output of the model is accurate)
 - c. Amount of input data necessary
 - d. Versatile and adaptable model (model can use different kinds of data as input and adapt to new input when necessary)

- e. Computational efficiency/time (model runs quickly and does not use a lot of CPU/GPU power)
 - f. Robustness (able to handle bias in the input data)
 - g. Large forecasting horizon (model can focus on different time horizons and is usable for every timeframe)
4. Accountability (how the model could be reused, and applied to gain value)
- a. FAIR use of data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable use of data)
 - b. Focus on environmental gain (model is mainly focused on lowering environmental stress and improving RES use)
 - c. Unparameterized model (open source) (Model is usable by other companies or different situations)

Appendix B

Resulting criteria list from the initial list

1. Security
 - a. Secure against model inversion attack (model complexity high enough that the model cannot be reproduced from the output, linear model is easy to replicate using output)
 - b. User of the model cannot access private data (model privacy) (Input data is not shared through the model/ cannot be accessed through the model)
2. Interpretability
 - a. Explainability (forecasted values (and the process) should be explainable to stakeholders)
 - b. Be able to link the model input to output in a visual way (no black box, able to follow reasons/logic of the model)
 - c. Output is in a logical range (the output of the model is consistent even with varying input)
 - d. Able to assess the quality of input data (model can determine the quality of the input data and give a proper indication)
 - e. Be able to show feature importance and selection of input data (the reasoning of the model can be followed on how it interprets and uses the input data)
 - f. Detecting and revealing anomalies in input data (model can determine the level of bias in the input data)
 - g. Graphical interface completeness (the model interface is easy to use)
 - h. Able to trace past decision-making (the output can be traced back to the specific input data)

- i. Easy to (re)implement (model is easy to use with few complex operations)
 - j. Risk minimalization by human overseeing (Human in the loop) (Errors are stated and can be fixed by a human operator)
 - k. Easy to incorporate with standard open source material (model can be used in combination with other (already existing) models)
3. Performance
- a. Able to finetune during operation (able to control the model during the whole process)
 - b. Model accuracy (output of the model is accurate)
 - c. Amount of input data necessary
 - d. Versatile and adaptable model (model can use different kinds of data as input and adapt to new input when necessary)
 - e. Computational efficiency/time (model runs quickly and does not use a lot of CPU/GPU power)
 - f. Robustness (able to handle bias in the input data)
 - g. Large forecasting horizon (model can focus on different time horizons and is usable for every timeframe)
4. Accountability (how the model could be reused, and applied to gain value)
- a. FAIR use of data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable use of data)
 - b. Focus on environmental gain (model is mainly focused on lowering environmental stress and improving RES use)
 - c. Unparameterized model (open source) (Model is usable by other companies or different situations)

Appendix C

Main criteria comparisons matrix for other two participants A, B and C

	Security	Interpretability	Performance	Accountability
Security	1	1/3	1/9	1/5
Interpretability	3	1	1/7	1
Performance	9	7	1	5
Accountability	5	1	1/5	1

	Security	Interpretability	Performance	Accountability
Security	1	1/9	1/9	1/9
Interpretability	9	1	1/3	1
Performance	9	3	1	1/3
Accountability	9	1	3	1

	Security	Interpretability	Performance	Accountability
Security	1	1	3	1/3
Interpretability	1	1	5	3
Performance	1/3	1/5	1	3
Accountability	3	1/3	1/3	1